

THERMAL-CHEMICAL FRACTIONATION OF LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOMASS

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ABSTRACT: Biomass is a valuable, sustainable feedstock for the production of chemicals and materials, and will play an important role in the transition towards a Sustainable Process Industry. Bio-based products – products wholly or partly derived from materials of biological origin – can make the society more sustainable and lower its dependence on fossil fuels. For the optimal utilization of bio-resources, fractionation on the basis of functionalities is often desired. Most commonly, biomass is separated into its main constituents lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose by steam or acid treatment. Thermochemical fractionation is an alternative, innovative two-step conversion process to transform different bio-resources into raw-materials for renewable chemicals and products. In this approach, a short thermal treatment at elevated temperature (fast pyrolysis) is followed by a low temperature fractionation of the mineral free, liquid product (FPBO) that keeps the key chemical functionalities intact in separate, liquid, depolymerized fractions. These fractions consist of components derived from the de-polymerization of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin.

Both the fractionation of FPBO and the use of the fractions in bio-based products are further developed in the EU-funded project called Bio4Products and Interreg project “Groen Goud”. The application of the pyrolytic fractions will be demonstrated in a number of end products such as phenolic resins, sand foundry moulding resins, paints, engineered wood and natural fibre reinforced products.

Exploratory research on both the fractionation and the applications has been carried out at bench-scale using pyrolysis oil derived from different types of biomass. Results were very positive and larger quantities of pyrolytic fractions are required for further product development and demonstration. Recently, a dedicated fractionation unit with a throughput capacity of 3 ton FPBO/day has been designed, constructed and commissioned.

Keywords: Fast Pyrolysis, fractionation, demonstration, biomass, pilot plant, TCF, thermochemical

1 INTRODUCTION

Pyrolysis is the thermal decomposition of organic material in an oxygen-free environment, and it results in solid, liquid and gaseous products. Fast pyrolysis is applied when the aim is to maximize the liquid yield. In this context fast relates to the rapid heating of the organic material.

Typically, the process is carried out at ambient pressures and a reactor temperatures of around 500°C. The biomass is rapidly heated and the vapour stream is rapidly cooled to avoid further reactions, and to maximize the yield of liquids. In case of clean woody biomass (e.g. pine wood) the liquid yield can be up to 70 wt%; about 15 wt% of the biomass is converted into charcoal and the remaining 15 wt% to non-condensable gases (e.g. CO, CO₂, CH₄).

The liquid product is often called Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (FPBO), although its properties do not justify to call it an oil. It is polar, acidic, contains water, and it is immiscible with fossil oils. It can be seen as a very broad mixture of components derived from the depolymerisation of cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin components of the feedstock.

Nowadays, clean wood-based FPBO is commercially used to replace fossil heavy fuel oils and natural gas in boiler applications. In Europe, commercial sized fast pyrolysis plants (> 10 MWth) are operational in Joensuu, Finland (Fortum), and in Hengelo (Empyro), the Netherlands [1]. Recently, the realisation of a new plant was announced by GreenFuelNordic (Lieska, Finland), which is more or less identical to the Empyro plant. The Empyro plant is based on the BTG fast pyrolysis process, and –by the end of 2018- Empyro has produced over 30 million litres of FPBO. Empyro is a polygeneration plant and an overall energetic efficiency of over 85% is achieved (pyrolysis oil, process steam &

electricity). Nearly all the oil produced is supplied to a dairy company and used as a co-feed in a process steam boiler combined with natural gas. The FPBO complies with the European standard for FPBO fuel for use in industrial boilers (EN 16900:2017).

The very short heating time in the fast pyrolysis process results in a liquid product containing fragments of the original biomass. This means that the original chemical functionalities present in the biomass are largely retained. In the fractionation process the FPBO is separated into different fractions with specific functionalities like extractives, carbohydrates/sugars and lignin/phenolics, see **Fig. 1**. Each fraction can be used as renewable raw material for a wide variety of end products.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the 2-step Thermo-Chemical Fractionation (TCF) process.

Alternatively, the approach of staged or fractional condensation is often proposed in literature [2,3]. The production of the various fractions is an integral part of the process by operating a number of condensers at different temperatures. A separation of components on the basis of boiling point/vapor pressure will be obtained. This is principally different from the TCF process in which a separation on the basis of solubility in specific solvents is achieved, and a better separation on functionalities can be expected.

The development of the TCF process as well as the application of the fractions in bio-based products is the subject of the European project Bio4Products (<http://www.bio4products.eu>) and the Interreg project Grünes Gold (www.groen-goud.eu). The focus of this paper is on the development of the fractionation process.

2 THERMO-CHEMICAL FRACTIONATION (TCF)

As mentioned above the TCF process can be divided in two steps being i) production of the pyrolysis liquid, and ii) the fractionation of the liquid in fractions with specific properties or chemical functionalities. The production and separation can be decoupled in time and scale.

The fractionation process is based on liquid-liquid extraction by organic or aqueous extractants. An organic extractant is used to separate the extractives from the oil; an aqueous extractant is suitable to separate pyrolytic lignin from the FPBO. The first step –extractives removal- is optional and not always required or desired, and a.o. depends on the biomass used in the pyrolysis process. Schematically, the fractionation step is shown in **Fig. 2**.

Fig. 2: Schematic representation of the FPBO fractionation process.

Biomass containing resin- and terpene like components will obviously result in a higher production of extractives. These components can be found in f.i. bark, roots, needles, etc. Removing the extractives from the pyrolysis oil will benefit in two ways. Removal of the extractives will result in a more homogenous pyrolysis oil [2]. Secondly, the recovery of the extractives can lead to a stream with unique chemical properties, which could serve as a raw material for specialty chemicals (analogous to “Pine chemicals”). The extractives stream is also likely to be quite similar in nature to tall-oil like liquids, and could probably be used as co-feed to produce diesel like products by HDO. However, the absolute amounts are relatively low. The organic extractant, e.g. heptane, octane or other higher non-polar solvent, will be recycled within the process.

The separation of the pyrolytic sugar stream (derived from cellulose and hemicellulose) and a liquid pyrolytic lignin stream (depolymerized lignin) is based on liquid-liquid extraction using an aqueous extractant. The extractant will end-up in the pyrolytic sugar stream, and depending on the specific use of this stream the extractant or part of it might be recycled within the process (e.g. if lower water content is desired). The extractives are produced in the first extraction step and the pyrolytic sugar and pyrolytic lignin in the second extraction step as is illustrated in **Fig. 2**. Depending on the biomass used,

there can be a difference in oil yield and in the ratio of obtained fractions.

Obviously, the ratio of extractives, lignin, cellulose and hemi-cellulose in the original biomass will influence the amounts of the individual fractions obtained. This has been subject of further research on lab-scale. Biomass feedstocks originating from different resources (e.g. residues from forestry, food/feed, agriculture) were tested in the thermo-chemical fractionation on lab-scale. Each feedstock was processed in a small pyrolysis unit to produce the FPBO and subsequently the liquid product was fractionated in the two-step, batch-wise extraction approach. In the first step the FPBO was extracted with an organic solvent in a separation funnel under severe shaking. The funnel content was left to settle (separate) for 2 - 4 hours and a clear separation was obtained between the organic extractant and the ‘extractives-free’ FPBO. The extractives were obtained by evaporation of the organic extractant. The remaining FPBO is intensively mixed (severe shaking) with the aqueous extractant (water) and left overnight to settle. The TCF results (pyrolysis and fractionation) of seven feeds tested are shown in **Fig. 3**. The liquid yield from the pyrolysis process is the sum of the extractives (EX), pyrolytic lignin (PL) and the pyrolytic sugars (PS). The yield is calculated on an extractant free basis.

Fig. 3: Yields of pyrolysis products obtained from different biomass feedstocks (as measured, not normalized)

The highest yield of FPBO was obtained with the softwood feed; this feed also resulted in the highest yield of PS. Highest yield of PL was obtained with softwood and straw. Extractives were mainly obtained from the sunflower husk and olive stones, likely due to remaining vegetable oil in the residues (sunflower oil and olive oil).

3 TYPICAL PROPERTIES OF FPBO AND THE FRACTIONS

The term oil in Fast Pyrolysis Oil (FPBO) is somewhat misleading as it does not show typical oil properties. FPBO is a complex, relative polar mixture of liquefied biomass which can contain up to 25 wt. % of water. FPBO has a high oxygen content and has a pH of ~2.9, due to the presence of organic acids including acetic acid, formic acid and propionic acid. The LHV of FPBO is about 19 MJ/L, which is about half the heating value of a fossil fuel.

In **Table I**, some properties of the FPBO and the separate fractions are given. The PS can be obtained with various water contents depending on the exact process configuration; in the table analytical data is given for relatively dry PS (“PS syrup”). Pyrolytic lignin is obtained from the fractionation process as a viscous liquid. After-treatment leads to a product which is solid at room temperature, and the properties of this solid lignin are given (S-PL).

Table I: Properties of FPBO and fractions

	FPBO	PS-S	S-PL	EX
C(wt%)	44.6	48.7	68.4	76.2
H (wt%)	7.1	6.7	6.2	10.4
N (wt%)	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
O (wt%)				
H ₂ O (wt%)	23.4	4.2	-	0.3
pH	2.9	-	-	-
Ash content (wt%)	0.1	0	0	0
TCN (mg BuO/g) ¹	146	118	-	4.9
TAN (mg KOH/g) ²	63	58	-	60
CR (wt%) ³	17	22	38	2
Mw (g/mole) ⁴	-	-	1,309	-
LHV (MJ/kg) ⁵	16.3	18.5	27.1	35.8

¹: TCN = Total Carbonyl Number, calculated in mg butanone/g sample. ²: TAN = Total Acid Number, calculated in mg KOH/g sample. ³: CR = Carbon Residue. Mw: Average molecular weight. ⁵: Lower Heating Value.

4 DEVELOPMENT OF A CONTINUOUS FRACTIONATION PROCESS

The lab-scale procedure for the fractionation of the FPBO has been translated into a continuous process, and demonstrated on bench and pilot scale.

4.1 Fractionation on bench-scale

At BTG a continuous bench-scale fractionation unit has been designed and constructed, see **Fig. 4**. The capacity is around 12.5 kg/h of FPBO input, and it consists of two extractor units. In the first unit the extractives are removed from the FPBO by using an organic solvent (heptane or similar). Recovery of the organic solvent is not integrated in this unit and performed off-line and batch-wise.

Fig. 4. Photo of the Bench-scale fractionation unit.

In the 2nd extractor the FPBO from the 1st step is extracted with water or an aqueous solution to obtain the PL and the PS. The unit uses a dedicated heating and

tracing system which ensures a fast steady separation. Furthermore, it allows to adequately control and monitor the ingoing feeds and the device temperatures. Multiple long-term fractionation runs with softwood derived FPBO have been executed, and in total more than 700 kg of FPBO was processed. It also results in significant amounts of lignin and sugar fractions required for initial development of new bio-based products using the fractions as raw material. The bench-scale unit has been used to further optimize the fractionation process and create a basis for scale-up to pilot plant scale.

4.3 Fractionation on pilot scale

A pilot plant fractionation unit has been designed based on the results and experience gained with the bench-scale unit. The design capacity of the pilot unit equals 3 ton of FPBO input per day, which is roughly a ten-fold scale-up of the bench-scale unit. Some pictures of the pilot unit are shown in **Fig. 5**.

Fig. 5: Photo's of the pilot fractionation plant.

The heart of the pilot plant are two extraction units: one for the extraction with an organic extractant and one for the separation with water or aqueous extractant. Evaporation units are included to allow for the recovery and/or recycling of the extractants. Additionally, the

lignin can be treated to obtain a solid lignin.

The construction of the pilot plant started in 2017 and was completed in the summer of 2018. An extensive commissioning programme was carried out in Q4-2018 to test all the instruments, controls, equipment and safety procedures. All sections have been successfully tested and initial production of larger quantities has been started. The actual input capacity achieved in the first test runs was just above 100 kg of FPBO per hour which is about 80 - 85% of the design capacity. The properties of the lignin and sugar fractions appeared to be very comparable to those produced in the bench-scale unit.

The focus is mainly on the production of pyrolytic sugars and solid pyrolytic lignin, see **Fig. 6**. To allow for the delivery of extended quantities activities have been started with respect to REACH registration of these fractions.

Fig. 5: Initial production of lignin from the pilot plant. A batch of 170 kg of S-PL

5 APPLICATIONS OF FPBO FRACTIONS

The use of FPBO as a boiler fuel is commercially proven in the Netherlands, Finland, Canada and the USA [1]. The use of specific fractions from FPBO as raw material for bio-based products is still in its infancy. The development of applications using the pyrolytic sugar and the pyrolytic lignin as raw material is extensively investigated in the projects Bio4Products and Grünes Gold.

Pyrolytic lignin can be used as a raw-material for the production of renewable bitumen or in various resins, as a replacement for fossil phenol. Especially in the latter, the chemical structure is of high importance. The type of phenol derivatives present and their amounts will be a measure for potential condensation reactions. It will also determine in which resin application this raw material can be used. The development of new products using pyrolytic lignin is led by Hexion GmbH from Germany. Although the pyrolytic lignin is not as reactive as the fossil phenol, it has shown to be much more reactive compared to other types of lignin such as natural or Kraft

lignin. Two types of promising pyrolytic lignin based resins were developed and successful tests have been performed on a 200 kg scale. Larger scale product testing (> 1 ton) are in a planning phase. In addition to resins the use of pyrolytic lignin in bio-based paints is developed and tested.

Differences in the chemical structure of the PS is believed to be much smaller and less pronounced compared to the PL. The current focus of the use of the pyrolytic sugars is in the production of modified wood. This work is led by the combination of TransFurans Chemical (TFC, Belgium) and Foreco from the Netherlands. Several formulations have been prepared by TFC and the most promising have been used by Foreco in a 1 m³ pilot pressure/vacuum impregnation unit. Based on the promising results demonstration field tests are planned within the next year.

6 SUMMARY

Biomass is a valuable, sustainable feedstock for the production of chemicals and materials. For the optimal utilization of bio-resources, fractionation on the basis of functionalities is often preferred. In this paper an innovative two-step conversion process to transform different bio-resources into raw-materials for renewable chemicals and products is presented; this approach is referred to as ThermoChemical Fractionation (TCF). In the first step the biomass feed is treated by fast pyrolysis resulting in a liquid product. Due to the fast and short heating the biomass is partly depolymerized, but key functionalities are retained in the liquid. In the second step the liquid is separated at low temperature by a liquid-liquid extraction process. The fractions consist of components derived from the de-polymerization of extractives, cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin.

A range of biomass feedstocks were tested in the thermo-chemical fractionation. These results demonstrated that TCF is a suitable process to convert residual biomass feeds originating from different resources into functional fractions that can subsequently be used as a raw-material in various product applications. Initially, a continuous-flow, bench-scale fractionation unit –capacity of 12.5 kg/h of FPBO- has been used to develop and optimize the process. Moreover, it provided the raw material required for developing and testing of new bio-based products.

On basis of the results obtained with the bench-scale unit a 3 t/d pilot plant –a tenfold scale-up- was designed and constructed. Successful commissioning of the pilot-plant took place in the last quarter of 2018. The properties of the fractions –in particular the lignin and sugar fractions- obtained with the pilot plant are very similar to those produced in the bench-scale unit.

The application of the pyrolytic fractions will be demonstrated in a number of end products such as phenolic resins, sand moulding resins, and engineered wood and natural fibre reinforced products. Demonstration/field tests are foreseen for 2019 and 2020. Due to the fact that quantities exceeding 1 t/y are foreseen to facilitate proper product testing a REACH registration will already be needed for each fraction.

7 ABBREVIATIONS

TCF	Thermo-Chemical Fractionation
FPBO	Fast Pyrolysis Bio-oil
PL	Pyrolytic Lignin
S-PL	Solid Pyrolytic Lignin
EX	Extractives
PS	Pyrolytic Sugar
PS-S	Pyrolytic Sugar Syrup
FP	Fractionation Plant
PP	Pyrolysis Plant

8 REFERENCES

- [1] EMPYRO: Implementation of a commercial scale fast pyrolysis plant in the Netherlands, Bert van de Beld and Gerhard Muggen, 23rd European Biomass Conference and Exhibition, Vienna-Austria (2015) 1670-1673.
- [2] Fractionation of flash pyrolysis condensates by staged condensation, Tim Schulzke, Stefan Conrad, Jan Westermeyer, Biomass and Bioenergy, vol 95 (2016), pp 287-295.
- [3] Recent developments in fast pyrolysis of lignocellulosic materials, Sascha Kersten, Manuel Garcia-Perez, Current opinion in Biotechnology, vol 24(3) (2013), pp 414-420.
- [4] Recovery of extractives from fast pyrolysis bio oil, Evert Leijenhorst, Hans Heeres, Bert van de Beld, Taina Ohra-aho, Anja Oasmaa, Christian Lindfors, 27th European Biomass Conference and Exhibition, 27-30 May 2019, Lisbon, Portugal (2019).

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